

The Role of Higher Mathematics as an Academic Discipline in the Modern Pattern of Higher Education on the Example of the Institute of Civil Engineering of the Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University

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Abstract. *The role of Mathematics and Higher Mathematics as academic disciplines in the structure of higher education is considered, the aims and tasks of its teaching are discussed, and the academic approach to teaching of the course of Higher Mathematics at the Institute of Civil Engineering of the Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University is briefly outlined.*

Keywords: *teaching of Higher Mathematics, algorithmic thinking, mathematical modeling, distant learning, academic performance monitoring, teaching methods.*

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Аннотация. *Рассматривается роль математики в целом и высшей математики в частности как академической дисциплины в структуре высшего образования, обсуждаются цели и задачи ее преподавания, а также описывается академический подход к выполнению таковых задач на примере Инженерно-строительного института Санкт-Петербургского политехнического университета Петра Великого.*

Ключевые слова: *преподавание высшей математики в ВУЗе, алгоритмическое мышление, математическое моделирование, дистанционное обучение, контроль успеваемости, методика преподавания.*

“Mathematics is similar to Art – and it is so not due to the fact, that Mathematics serves us as “the art of calculations” or as “the art of proofs”, but due to the fact, that Mathematics, as well as Art is, represents a special manner of Cognition”. These remarkably fair words belong to Vladimir Uspenskiy, a winner of the “Educator” award and the author of the excellent book “The apology of Mathematics” [5].

Considering mathematics in general and higher mathematics in particular as academic disciplines, one can see the purpose of their study is for students to master the mathematical apparatus necessary for analysis, mathematical modeling and, as a result, the successful solution of production, organizational and managerial tasks that their future independent professional activity will offer them in our rapidly changing and undergoing total digitalization world [1, 2].

In the light of the provisions formulated above, the tasks of teaching this academic discipline are seen primarily in the development of logical and algorithmic thinking among students, in teaching methods of solving mathematically formalized problems, in forming their personal skills of working with mathematical literature. Students should understand both the essence of mathematical methods and the techniques of their use in solving technical and creative engineering problems [3, 8], related to modern technologies and the organization of companies’ activities.

Thus, the course of the discipline “Higher mathematics” is the fundamental basis of the whole building of contemporary educational system on all its levels. The course has to be designed both to teach a student special knowledge and to lay down specific skills, to form

special skills that make up general and professional competencies, namely:

- willingness and readiness to use mathematical modeling and analysis methods in experimental research and, as a result, in engineering developments [10, 11, 12];

- the ability to abstract perception of information, to generalizing analysis and, based on the results of such analysis, the ability to choose goals, set tasks, determine ways to achieve the goals set, and successfully solve the formulated tasks independently [3, 4];

- readiness, under the conditions of rapid development of modern science and technology, within the framework of changing social practice, to analyze their capabilities and critically reassess existing experience; the desire to acquire and accumulate new knowledge, to use new technologies, including educational techniques and computer technologies [5, 6];

- the ability to work individually, independently and creatively, to make fruitful decisions primarily in the field of professional competence [6, 7];

- skills of using methods of acquiring, storing and processing information, compliance with the principles and requirements of information security [3].

The academic discipline “Higher mathematics” in accordance with the current curricula, is studied at the Institute of Civil Engineering of the Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University, where both authors have the honor to teach it, during the first two semesters, and belongs to the set of basic academic disciplines.

The evaluation of the results of students’ educational activities, the quality of their knowledge, skills and ac-

quired professional competencies is carried out on a traditional three-point scale, including such gradations as “satisfactory”, “good” and “excellent”.

A student's academic performance is characterized by an examination grade for a semester. The system of ongoing control is designed to cover all topics of the course of discipline. Intermediate intra-semester assessments, namely: monthly attestation, as well as the grades given to the student based on the results of their verification works and individual homework, play the role of rating assessments.

Exam grades are indicated in the student's individual record book. The semester exam according to the working programs of the discipline in the various areas of educating of students within the Institute can be conducted orally, in writing or in the form of a test, and can also take into account the portfolio formed for each student according to his or her rating intra-semester results.

With the distance learning format, the same forms of examinations are implemented on the website of the

Distance Learning System of the Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University.

The course program is implemented in streaming lectures and practical classes in study groups. The lectures present the bulk of the theoretical material, analyze typical examples of problems solving. The main theorems in the lecture course are proved, the formulas are strictly and clearly deduced.

Only under the conditions listed in the previous paragraph can a student develop evidence-based algorithmic thinking and mathematical culture [13, 14]. The main purpose of practical classes is seen in the development of the student's skills and abilities used in applications of mathematics [9, 15, 16].

In the case of distant learning, all lectures and practical classes are conducted through the website of the Distant Learning System of the Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University in real time in compliance with the grid of the academic schedule. Their records are available to students for viewing and copying during the year after the lesson.

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